

Expanded Table 1 for Leaving Flatland: Advances in 3D behavioral measurement

Jesse D. Marshall, Tianqing Li, Joshua H. Wu, Timothy W. Dunn

Current Opinion in Neurobiology (2022)

Emerging directions in 3D human and animal tracking. Thematically organized compilation of recent studies that illustrate a roadmap for improvements in 3D behavioral tracking based on computer vision and deep learning.

			Human 3D Tracking	Animal 3D Tracking
Occlusion robustness	Multi-view inputs	2D cross-view fusion + triangulation	[1] [2] [3] [4] [5]	
		2D keypoint triangulation	[6]	[7] [8] [9]
		3D volumetric	[6] [10]	[11] [12]
	Temporal information		[13] [14] [15] [16] [17]	[9] [8] [18] [19]
	Graphical modeling		[20] [1] [21] [22] [23]	[24]
	Explicit occlusion training		[25] [26]	
Labeled training data efficiency	Multi-view consistency		[27] [28] [29] [30] [31]	[32] [19]
	Geometric self-supervision		[33] [34] [13] [35] [36]	
	Representation learning		[37] [38] [39] [40] [41]	[19]
	Constraints		[42] [43]	[8]
	Data augmentation		[44] [45]	

Flexible, scalable and rapid tracking	Unsynchronized or uncalibrated cameras	[46] [47] [42] [48] [49]	
	Real-time tracking	[50] [51] [52] [53]	
Richer body representations	Dense pose estimation	[54] [55]	[56] [19]
	Body shape reconstruction	[57] [58] [59] [60]	[61] [62] [63] [64]
Multi-subject tracking	Top-down approaches	[65] [66] [67] [10] [5] [68]	[69] [70]
	Bottom-up approaches	[71] [39] [72]	
	Interaction modeling	[73] [74] [75]	
3D pose uncertainty	Multi-pose generation	[76] [77]	
	Probabilistic modeling	[78] [79]	[24]
Datasets	3D pose	[80] [81] [82] [83] [84] [85]	[86] [69] [87] [88] [70] [12]
	3D shape	[89] [90] [91] [92]	[87]
	Synthetic data	[93] [94] [95] [96] [97]	[64] [98]

References:

1. Qiu H, Wang C, Wang J, Wang N, Zeng W: **Cross view fusion for 3d human pose estimation**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2019:4342–4351.
2. He Y, Yan R, Fragkiadaki K, Yu S-I: **Epipolar Transformer for Multi-view Human Pose Estimation**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops*. 2020:1036–1037.
3. Xie R, Wang C, Wang Y: **Metafuse: A pre-trained fusion model for human pose estimation**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2020:13686–13695.
4. Zhang Z, Wang C, Qiu W, Qin W, Zeng W: **AdaFuse: Adaptive Multiview Fusion for Accurate Human Pose Estimation in the Wild**. *International Journal of Computer Vision* 2021, **129**:703–718.

5. Lin J, Lee GH: **Multi-View Multi-Person 3D Pose Estimation with Plane Sweep Stereo**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2021:11886–11895.
6. Iskakov K, Burkov E, Lempitsky V, Malkov Y: **Learnable triangulation of human pose**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2019:7718–7727.
7. Nath T, Mathis A, Chen AC, Patel A, Bethge M, Mathis MW: **Using DeepLabCut for 3D markerless pose estimation across species and behaviors**. *Nature protocols* 2018, doi:10.1038/s41596-019-0176-0.
8. Karashchuk P, Rupp KL, Dickinson ES, Walling-Bell S, Sanders E, Azim E, Brunton BW, Tuthill JC: **Anipose: A toolkit for robust markerless 3D pose estimation**. *Cell Rep* 2021, **36**:109730.
9. Liu X, Yu S-Y, Flierman NA, Loyola S, Kamermans M, Hoogland TM, De Zeeuw CI: **OptiFlex: Multi-Frame Animal Pose Estimation Combining Deep Learning With Optical Flow**. *Frontiers in cellular neuroscience* 2021, **15**.
10. Tu H, Wang C, Zeng W: **VoxelPose: Towards Multi-camera 3D Human Pose Estimation in Wild Environment**. In *Computer Vision – ECCV 2020*. Springer International Publishing; 2020:197–212.
11. Zimmermann C, Schneider A, Alyahyay M, Brox T: **Freipose: A deep learning framework for precise animal motion capture in 3d spaces**. *BioRxiv* 2020, doi:10.1101/2020.02.27.967620.
12. Dunn TW, Marshall JD, Severson KS, Aldarondo DE, Hildebrand DGC, Chettih SN, Wang WL, Gellis AJ, Carlson DE, Aronov D, et al.: **Geometric deep learning enables 3D kinematic profiling across species and environments**. *Nature methods* 2021, **18**:564–573.
13. Pavlo D, Feichtenhofer C, Grangier D, Auli M: **3d human pose estimation in video with temporal convolutions and semi-supervised training**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019:7753–7762.
14. Rafi U, Doering A, Leibe B, Gall J: **Self-supervised Keypoint Correspondences for Multi-person Pose Estimation and Tracking in Videos**. In *Computer Vision – ECCV 2020*. Springer International Publishing; 2020:36–52.
15. Zheng C, Zhu S, Mendieta M, Yang T, Chen C, Ding Z: **3D Human Pose Estimation with Spatial and Temporal Transformers**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2021:11656–11665.
16. Choi H, Moon G, Chang JY, Lee KM: **Beyond Static Features for Temporally Consistent 3D Human Pose and Shape from a Video**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2021:1964–1973.

17. Li W, Liu H, Ding R, Liu M, Wang P, Yang W: **Exploiting Temporal Contexts with Strided Transformer for 3D Human Pose Estimation.** *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia* 2022,
18. Sarkar I, Maji I, Omprakash C, Stober S, Mikulovic S, Bauer P: **Evaluation of deep lift pose models for 3D rodent pose estimation based on geometrically triangulated data.** *arXiv [csCV]* 2021,
19. Bala PC, Zimmermann J, Park HS, Hayden BY: **Self-supervised Secondary Landmark Detection via 3D Representation Learning.** *arXiv [csCV]* 2021,
20. Cai Y, Ge L, Liu J, Cai J, Cham T-J, Yuan J, Thalmann NM: **Exploiting spatial-temporal relationships for 3d pose estimation via graph convolutional networks.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2019:2272–2281.
21. Zeng A, Sun X, Yang L, Zhao N, Liu M, Xu Q: **Learning Skeletal Graph Neural Networks for Hard 3D Pose Estimation.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2021:11436–11445.
22. Zou L, Huang Z, Gu N, Wang F, Yang Z, Wang G: **GMDN: A lightweight graph-based mixture density network for 3D human pose regression.** *Computers & Graphics* 2021, **95**:115–122.
23. Xu T, Takano W: **Graph Stacked Hourglass Networks for 3D Human Pose Estimation.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2021:16105–16114.
24. Zhang L, Dunn T, Marshall J, Olveczky B, Linderman S: **Animal pose estimation from video data with a hierarchical von Mises-Fisher-Gaussian model.** In *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*. PMLR; 2021:2800–2808.
25. Cheng Y, Yang B, Wang B, Yan W, Tan RT: **Occlusion-aware networks for 3d human pose estimation in video.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2019:723–732.
26. Cheng Y, Yang B, Wang B, Tan RT: **3D Human Pose Estimation Using Spatio-Temporal Networks with Explicit Occlusion Training.** *AAAI* 2020, **34**:10631–10638.
27. Mitra R, Gundavarapu NB, Sharma A, Jain A: **Multiview-consistent semi-supervised learning for 3d human pose estimation.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2020:6907–6916.
28. Jenni S, Favaro P: **Self-Supervised Multi-View Synchronization Learning for 3D Pose Estimation.** In *Proceedings of the Asian Conference on Computer Vision*. 2020.
29. Wandt, B., Rudolph, M., Zell, P., Rhodin, H., & Rosenhahn, B.: **CanonPose: Self-supervised monocular 3D human pose**

- estimation in the wild.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2021:13294–13304.
30. Iqbal U, Molchanov P, Kautz J: **Weakly-supervised 3d human pose learning via multi-view images in the wild.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2020:5243–5252.
 31. Usman B, Tagliasacchi A, Saenko K, Sud A: **MetaPose: Fast 3D Pose from Multiple Views without 3D Supervision.** *arXiv [csCV] 2021*,
 32. Yao Y, Jafarian Y, Park HS: **MONET: Multiview Semi-supervised Keypoint Detection via Epipolar Divergence.** *arXiv [csCV] 2018*,
 33. Chen C-H, Tyagi A, Agrawal A, Drover D, Stojanov S, Rehg JM: **Unsupervised 3d pose estimation with geometric self-supervision.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019:5714–5724.
 34. Kocabas M, Karagoz S, Akbas E: **Self-supervised learning of 3d human pose using multi-view geometry.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019:1077–1086.
 35. Li Y, Li K, Jiang S, Zhang Z, Huang C, Da Xu RY: **Geometry-Driven Self-Supervised Method for 3D Human Pose Estimation.** In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. 2020:11442–11449.
 36. Wang K, Lin L, Jiang C, Qian C, Wei P: **3D Human Pose Machines with Self-Supervised Learning.** *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 2019, **42**:1069–1082.
 37. Jiang M, Yu Z, Zhang Y, Wang Q, Li C, Lei Y: **Reweighted sparse representation with residual compensation for 3D human pose estimation from a single RGB image.** *Neurocomputing* 2019, **358**:332–343.
 38. Chen X, Lin K-Y, Liu W, Qian C, Lin L: **Weakly-supervised discovery of geometry-aware representation for 3d human pose estimation.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019:10895–10904.
 39. Kundu JN, Revanur A, Waghmare GV, Venkatesh RM, Babu RV: **Unsupervised Cross-Modal Alignment for Multi-person 3D Pose Estimation.** In *Computer Vision – ECCV 2020*. Springer International Publishing; 2020:35–52.
 40. Sun JJ, Zhao J, Chen L-C, Schroff F, Adam H, Liu T: **View-Invariant Probabilistic Embedding for Human Pose.** In *Computer Vision – ECCV 2020*. Springer International Publishing; 2020:53–70.
 41. Zimmermann C, Argus M, Brox T: **Contrastive Representation Learning for Hand Shape Estimation.** *arXiv [csCV] 2021*, doi:10.1109/ICCV.2019.00090.

42. Ma Z, Yao Y, Ji P, Ma C: **Learning Transferable Kinematic Dictionary for 3D Human Pose and Shape Reconstruction.** *arXiv [csCV] 2021,*
43. Liu S, Huang X, Fu N, Ostadabbas S: **Heuristic Weakly Supervised 3D Human Pose Estimation in Novel Contexts without Any 3D Pose Ground Truth.** *arXiv [csCV] 2021,*
44. Zeng A, Sun X, Huang F, Liu M, Xu Q, Lin S: **SRNet: Improving Generalization in 3D Human Pose Estimation with a Split-and-Recombine Approach.** In *Computer Vision – ECCV 2020.* Springer International Publishing; 2020:507–523.
45. Li S, Ke L, Pratama K, Tai Y-W, Tang C-K, Cheng K-T: **Cascaded deep monocular 3D human pose estimation with evolutionary training data.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition.* 2020:6173–6183.
46. Yoon JS, Shiratori T, Yu SI, Park HS: **Self-supervised adaptation of high-fidelity face models for monocular performance tracking.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition.* 2019:4601–4609.
47. Kundu JN, Seth S, Rahul MV, Rakesh M, Radhakrishnan VB, Chakraborty A: **Kinematic-Structure-Preserved Representation for Unsupervised 3D Human Pose Estimation.** *AAAI 2020,* **34:**11312–11319.
48. Chen X, Wei P, Lin L: **Deductive Learning for Weakly-Supervised 3D Human Pose Estimation via Uncalibrated Cameras.** In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence.* 2021:1089–1096.
49. Kocabas M, Huang C-HP, Tesch J, Muller L, Hilliges O, Black MJ: **SPEC: Seeing People in the Wild with an Estimated Camera.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision.* 2021:11035–11045.
50. Ren P, Sun H, Qi Q, Wang J, Huang W: **SRN: Stacked Regression Network for Real-time 3D Hand Pose Estimation.** *BMVC 2019,*
51. Hwang D-H, Kim S, Monet N, Koike H, Bae S: **Lightweight 3D human pose estimation network training using teacher-student learning.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision.* 2020:479–488.
52. Remelli E, Han S, Honari S, Fua P, Wang R: **Lightweight Multi-View 3D Pose Estimation through Camera-Disentangled Representation.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition.* 2020:6040–6049.
53. Choi S, Choi S, Kim C: **MobileHumanPose: Toward Real-Time 3D Human Pose Estimation in Mobile Devices.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition.* 2021:2328–2338.

54. Neverova N, Thewlis J, Guler RA, Kokkinos I, Vedaldi A: **Slim densepose: Thrifty learning from sparse annotations and motion cues.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019:10915–10923.
55. Weinzaepfel P, Brégier R, Combaluzier H, Leroy V, Rogez G: **DOPE: Distillation of Part Experts for Whole-Body 3D Pose Estimation in the Wild.** In *ECCV 2020*. 2020:380–397.
56. Sanakoyeu A, Khalidov V, McCarthy MS, Vedaldi A, Neverova N: **Transferring dense pose to proximal animal classes.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2020:5233–5242.
57. Pavlakos G, Choutas V, Ghorbani N, Bolkart T, Osman AAA, Tzionas D, Black MJ: **Expressive body capture: 3d hands, face, and body from a single image.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019:10975–10985.
58. Jiang W, Kolotouros N, Pavlakos G, Zhou X, Daniilidis K: **Coherent reconstruction of multiple humans from a single image.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2020:5579–5588.
59. Xu H, Bazavan EG, Zanfir A, Freeman WT, Sukthankar R, Sminchisescu C: **Ghum & ghumi: Generative 3d human shape and articulated pose models.** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2020:6184–6193.
60. Zheng Z, Yu T, Liu Y, Dai Q: **PaMIR: Parametric Model-Conditioned Implicit Representation for Image-based Human Reconstruction.** *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 2021, doi:10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3050505.
61. Zuffi, S., Kanazawa, A., Berger-Wolf, T., & Black, M. J.: **Three-D Safari: Learning to Estimate Zebra Pose, Shape, and Texture from Images“ In the Wild.”** In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2019:5359–5368.
62. Biggs B, Boyne O, Charles J, Fitzgibbon A, Cipolla R: **Who Left the Dogs Out? 3D Animal Reconstruction with Expectation Maximization in the Loop.** In *Computer Vision – ECCV 2020*. Springer International Publishing; 2020:195–211.
63. Li C, Ghorbani N, Broomé S, Rashid M: **hSMAL: Detailed Horse Shape and Pose Reconstruction for Motion Pattern Recognition.** *arXiv preprint arXiv* 2021,
64. Deane J, Kearney S, Kim KI, Cosker D: **DynaDog+T: A Parametric Animal Model for Synthetic Canine Image Generation.** *arXiv [csCV]* 2021,
65. Dabral R, Gundavarapu NB, Mitra R, Sharma A, Ramakrishnan G, Jain A: **Multi-Person 3D Human Pose Estimation from Monocular Images.** In *2019 International Conference on 3D Vision (3DV)*. IEEE; 2019:405–414.

66. Dong J, Fang Q, Jiang W, Yang Y, Huang Q, Bao H, Zhou X: **Fast and Robust Multi-Person 3D Pose Estimation and Tracking from Multiple Views**. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 2021, doi:10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3098052.
67. Huang C, Jiang S, Li Y, Zhang Z, Traish J, Deng C, Ferguson S, Da Xu RY: **End-to-end Dynamic Matching Network for Multi-view Multi-person 3D Pose Estimation**. In *Computer Vision – ECCV 2020*. Springer International Publishing; 2020:477–493.
68. Reddy ND, Guigues L, Pishchulin L, Eledath J, Narasimhan SG: **TesseTrack: End-to-End Learnable Multi-Person Articulated 3D Pose Tracking**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2021:15190–15200.
69. Bala PC, Eisenreich BR, Yoo SBM, Hayden BY, Park HS, Zimmermann J: **Automated markerless pose estimation in freely moving macaques with OpenMonkeyStudio**. *Nature communications* 2020, 11:4560.
70. Marshall JD, Klibaite U, Gellis A, Aldarondo DE, Olveczky B, Dunn TW: **The PAIR-R24M Dataset for Multi-animal 3D Pose Estimation**. In *Thirty-fifth Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems Datasets and Benchmarks Track (Round 1)*. 2021.
71. Jin S, Liu W, Xie E, Wang W, Qian C, Ouyang W, Luo P: **Differentiable Hierarchical Graph Grouping for Multi-person Pose Estimation**. In *Computer Vision – ECCV 2020*. Springer International Publishing; 2020:718–734.
72. Dong Z, Song J, Chen X, Guo C, Hilliges O: **Shape-aware multi-person pose estimation from multi-view images**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2021:11158–11168.
73. Hasson Y, Varol G, Tzionas D, Kalevatykh I, Black MJ, Laptev I, Schmid C: **Learning joint reconstruction of hands and manipulated objects**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019:11807–11816.
74. Li Z, Sedlar J, Carpentier J, Laptev I, Mansard N, Sivic J: **Estimating 3d motion and forces of person-object interactions from monocular video**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019:8640–8649.
75. Fieraru M, Zanfir M, Oneata E, Popa A-I, Olaru V, Sminchisescu C: **Three-dimensional reconstruction of human interactions**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2020:7214–7223.
76. Li C, Lee GH: **Generating multiple hypotheses for 3d human pose estimation with mixture density network**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019:9887–9895.

77. Biggs B, Ehrhardt S, Joo H, Graham B, Vedaldi A, Novotny D: **3D Multi-bodies: Fitting Sets of Plausible 3D Human Models to Ambiguous Image Data**. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 33 (2020)*. 2020:20496–20507.
78. Kolotouros N, Pavlakos G, Jayaraman D, Daniilidis K: **Probabilistic Modeling for Human Mesh Recovery**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2021:11605–11614.
79. Wehrbein T, Rudolph M, Rosenhahn B, Wandt B: **Probabilistic monocular 3d human pose estimation with normalizing flows**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2021:11199–11208.
80. Sigal L, Balan AO, Black MJ: **HumanEva: Synchronized Video and Motion Capture Dataset and Baseline Algorithm for Evaluation of Articulated Human Motion**. *International journal of computer vision* 2009, **87**:4.
81. Ionescu C, Papava D, Olaru V, Sminchisescu C: **Human3.6M: Large Scale Datasets and Predictive Methods for 3D Human Sensing in Natural Environments**. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 2014, **36**:1325–1339.
82. Joo H, Liu H, Tan L, Gui L, Nabbe B, Matthews I, Kanade T, Nobuhara S, Sheikh Y: **Panoptic studio: A massively multiview system for social motion capture**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2015:3334–3342.
83. Mehta D, Rhodin H, Casas D, Fua P, Sotnychenko O, Xu W, Theobalt C: **Monocular 3D Human Pose Estimation In The Wild Using Improved CNN Supervision**. In *2017 international conference on 3D vision (3DV)*. IEEE; [date unknown]:506–516.
84. Lassner C, Romero J, Kiefel M, Bogo F, Black MJ, Gehler PV: **Unite the people: Closing the loop between 3d and 2d human representations**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2017:6050–6059.
85. von Marcard T, Henschel R, Black MJ, Rosenhahn B, Pons-Moll G: **Recovering accurate 3d human pose in the wild using imus and a moving camera**. In *Proceedings of the European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV)*. 2018:601–617.
86. Günel S, Rhodin H, Morales D, Campagnolo J, Ramdya P, Fua P: **DeepFly3D, a deep learning-based approach for 3D limb and appendage tracking in tethered, adult Drosophila**. *Elife* 2019, **8**.
87. Kearney S, Li W, Parsons M, Kim KI, Cosker D: **RGBD-dog: Predicting canine pose from RGBD sensors**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2020:8336–8345.
88. Joska D, Clark L, Muramatsu N, Jericevich R, Nicolls F, Mathis A, Mathis MW, Patel A: **AcinoSet: A 3D Pose Estimation Dataset and Baseline Models for Cheetahs in the Wild**. *arXiv [csCV]* 2021,
89. Varol G, Romero J, Martin X, Mahmood N, Black MJ, Laptev I, Schmid C: **Learning from Synthetic Humans**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2017:109–117.

90. Güler RA, Neverova N, Kokkinos I: **Densepose: Dense human pose estimation in the wild**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2018:7297–7306.
91. Mahmood N, Ghorbani N, Troje NF, Pons-Moll G, Black MJ: **AMASS: Archive of Motion Capture as Surface Shapes**. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*. 2019:5442–5451.
92. Choutas V, Pavlakos G, Bolkart T, Tzionas D, Black MJ: **Monocular Expressive Body Regression through Body-Driven Attention**. In *European Conference on Computer Vision*. Springer, Cham; 2020:20–40.
93. Doersch C, Zisserman A: **Sim2real transfer learning for 3D human pose estimation: motion to the rescue**. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*. 2019.
94. Wang Y, Liang W, Shen J, Jia Y, Yu L-F: **A deep Coarse-to-Fine network for head pose estimation from synthetic data**. *Pattern Recognit* 2019, **94**:196–206.
95. Zhang X, Wong Y, Kankanhalli MS, Geng W: **Unsupervised Domain Adaptation for 3D Human Pose Estimation**. In *Proceedings of the 27th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. Association for Computing Machinery; 2019:926–934.
96. Sengupta A, Budvytis I, Cipolla R: **Synthetic Training for Accurate 3D Human Pose and Shape Estimation in the Wild**. *arXiv [csCV]* 2020,
97. Varol G, Laptev I, Schmid C, Zisserman A: **Synthetic Humans for Action Recognition from Unseen Viewpoints**. *Int J Comput Vis* 2021, **129**:2264–2287.
98. Bolaños LA, Xiao D, Ford NL, LeDue JM, Gupta PK, Doebeli C, Hu H, Rhodin H, Murphy TH: **A three-dimensional virtual mouse generates synthetic training data for behavioral analysis**. *Nature methods* 2021, **18**:378–381.